

Human Resources Recruitment Defining Peculiarities of Students as Job Seekers

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Abstract—Some organizations as employers have difficulties to attract job seekers and retain their employees. Strategic planning of Human Resources (HR) presumes broad analysis of perspectives including analysis of potential job seekers in the field. Human Resources Recruitment (HRR) influences employer brand of an organization and peculiarities of both external organizational factors and stakeholders. Defining peculiarities of the future job seekers, who could potentially become the employees of the organization, could help to adjust HRR tools and methods adapt to the youngest generation employees' preferences and be more successful in selecting the best candidates, who are likely to be loyal to the employer. The aim of the empirical study is definition of some students' as job seekers peculiarities and their requirements to their potential employer. The survey in Latvia, Lithuania and Spain. Respondents were students from these countries' tertiary education institutions Public Administration (PA) or relevant study programs. All three countries students' peculiarities have just a slight difference. Overall, they all wish to work for a socially responsible employer that is able to provide positive working environment and possibilities for professional development and learning. However, respondents from each country have own peculiarities. The study might have a practical application. PA of the examined countries might use the results developing employer brand and creating job advertisements focusing on recent graduates' recruitment.

Keywords—Generation Y, human resources recruitment, public administration.

I. INTRODUCTION

SOME employers plan their HR towards strategic plans of organizations, considering both external and internal organizational environment factors. However, this might be a rural example of some other employers' activity. Based on previous researches results [1]-[4], the author concluded that PA as employer might be weaker in Human Resource Management activities that for example private sector employers in case of Latvia. Therefore, the author focuses on PA organizations as employees and PA study programs students, who are potentially the future employees of the PA organizations.

HRR is an activity that mostly connects employer with the potential employees from the external environment. Within this research the concept of HRR is defined as "the process of attracting prospective employees and stimulating them for applying job in an organization" [5]. Organization needs to be attractive enough to make students from relevant study programs apply to the vacant positions. To be able to do so, it

should have a positive employer brand and offer something valuable for employees. Therefore, the organization needs to explore their potential employees to be able to adapt to their preferences and values.

To compare students' requirements, the author conducts a survey to identify peculiarities of PA study programs university students from Latvia, Lithuania, and Spain. To be employed by PA it is not required to hold a degree in PA. However, PA study programs exist in these countries. It is possible to expect that students, who study PA, are planning to be employed by PA organizations. However, majority of these students are generation Y representatives i.e. they "want and expect more than preceding generations" [6] also from their employers.

This empirical study aims to identify some students' (from the population) as job seekers peculiarities and their requirements to their potential employer. The questionnaire [7] were developed based on previous researches results on employer branding [1], social responsibility [8], job advertisements' analysis [9] etc.

The study results are expected to have a practical application especially for the PA organizations of the examined countries. The results are valuable implementing a number of HR management activities such as employer branding, recruitment etc.

II. HR RECRUITMENT CHALLENGES OF FUTURE

The author of the present paper defines that "(...) organizations as employers should develop good relationships with their potential employees. (...) They are those people who could be (...) organizations key staff in the coming years. It is necessary to carefully assess the characteristics of Y generation specialists as a potential employees attracting and selecting new employees (...)" [10]. Especially psychologists and then management researches started to explore generation Y shortly before 2000, however, since millennium this topic has started to pick up their popularity. It is explainable by the fact that generation Y representatives are people born from 1980 till 2000 [11] - time of transition from the information society to the knowledge society [12], so they are about 16-36 years old by now and the oldest representatives are active and mature citizens as well as labor market players now. However, there is still lack of scientific researches that focus on generation Y as employers or job seekers.

HRR implementers should pay attention on this generation as job seekers examination identifying generation Y characteristics that might be relevant for employers during HRR process and all other relevant activities. They need to

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pay more attention on influence of the generation peculiarities to a choice of certain HRR strategy, tools, methods and approaches.

Mainly J. Matthewman focuses on Millennials (as generation Y is also called) exploration and characterization as a unique and new generation of employees that requires employers' need to have 'cool values' around the environment and society. He wrote, "Organizations need to change because Gen Y has different values as it is the only sure-fire recipe for disaster as Gen Y will be tomorrow's engine room of the organizations" [6].

Generation Y representatives are special job seekers and employees, therefore, the organizations need to find the certain approach to address them, to earn their attention and interest. Generation Y representatives are rather attracted by socially responsible organizations [6]. Nowadays employers need to adapt their HRR mechanisms to potential employees. Employers that recruit young specialists, e.g. recent graduates or even last year undergraduate or graduate students need to take into account typical characteristics of generation Y as job seekers into consideration that might differ depending on countries and background. Generally, generation Y representatives are characterized as [6], [11], [13], [14]: technology users, curious about the current situation on the spot, educated and fast learners, practical, enterprising, manipulative, not loyal to employers, etc. [15].

There are findings that prove that there are peculiarities of unemployed people and some organizations activities have greater impact on them than some external factors e.g. "work-role centrality, coping resources (personal, social, financial, and time structure), cognitive appraisals, and coping strategies displayed stronger relationships with mental health than did human capital or demographic variables" [16].

From one hand, the End of History Illusion proves that people change their opinions, minds, habits and preferences while growing and developing. Young people in their twenties most probably will have different priorities and preferences in their thirties that they have now even they are thinking that they will not change them aging [17]. Therefore, the effect is not long lasting. Adapting to the young generation job seekers and employees now employers need to realize that they cannot treat them in the same way during their early aging period. In addition, earliest youth employment studies showed that "early employment experience has virtually no effect on later employment after controlling for persistent characteristics of individuals, such as education" [18]. From another hand, longitudinal studies show that "a person's unemployment experience when young is correlated with their later adult employment patterns' and it does not depend on the young people background" [19] i.e. it is crucial to explore the causes of unemployment to seek economy sustainability and mentally healthy population. It requires also a right action from the employers' side.

Branding is important for Millennials. Organizations, recognizing all peculiarities of generation Y representatives, should focus on employer brand creation and development actively using modern technologies and communication

resources to attract young job seekers. Generation Y representatives are active, educated, practical and idealistic as personalities and as job seekers and employees. Organizations task is to consider all these and a list of other generation Y peculiarities as well as define them as separate stakeholder group to choose the most relevant relationships creation and development strategy. Generation Y as job seekers and employees will be defined as different type of stakeholders for each organization.

With organization broader overview of HR planning and relationships development with generation Y job seekers with the relevant background, it as employer can succeed in HRR. It needs just get acquainted with the job seekers better.

III. RESEARCH POPULATION AND METHODOLOGY

Population of the study is defined as undergraduate (Bachelor level) and graduate (Master level) students of the tertiary education institutions PA or relevant study programs of Latvia, Lithuania and Spain in age from 18 to 24. The age frame was defined based on a number of criteria such as age of youth by law and statistics (that are issued to define youth employment/unemployment level), minimal possible age of undergraduate students etc. [7]. Convenient sample were used.

In case of Latvia, there are only graduate PA study programs, and age of the majority of the students is above 24 years, however their average age is 28 years, they are generation Y representatives, therefore they were also exceptionally selected as the respondents. It was defined that the difference in youngest and older respondents of Latvia preferences on a future job and employer is not significant, therefore the survey results will be represented considering all respondents from Latvia in spite of their age.

In case of Spain, a part of respondents were foreign students (non-Spanish citizens or residents), therefore their replies were excluded from the analysis as they have a significant difference from the local students' replies.

There are five universities that provide accredited PA study programs in Latvia. All these programs are Master's ones. Only three of them had full-time/part-time students in 2015/2016 academic year. Only one university – the University of Latvia students participated in the survey in 2015 (Table I).

There are six universities that provide accredited PA or relevant study programs in Lithuania. Six of them are Bachelor level programs, five of them are Master's programs. Three universities students participated in the survey (Table I).

20 universities of Spain provide PA or relevant study programs. 20 programs provided are Bachelor level programs, and nine programs are Master's ones. Students of two universities of Spain participated in the survey (Table I).

Questionnaires were adapted for each country and translated in the local language for the respondents from Latvia and Spain. The respondents from Lithuania had English version of the questionnaire. Both online and printed in-class questionnaires filling were applied. Online questionnaires were sent by the universities administration to all students from the sample.

TABLE I
CHARACTERISTICS OF THE DATA COLLECTED [20]-[26]

Number of respondents	Study level	Name of the Study Program	Name of the University	Country
11	Master's	Public Management	University of Latvia Kaunas	Latvia
7	Bachelor	PA	University of Technology Kaunas	Lithuania
5	Master's	PA	University of Technology Klaipėda	Lithuania
3	Bachelor	PA	University Mykolas Romeris	Lithuania
18	Bachelor	PA	University Complutense	Lithuania
24	Bachelor	Management and PA	University of Madrid	Spain
4	Bachelor	Political Science and Public Management	University of the Basque Country	Spain

The comparison of the respondents' replies is implemented by country. This research represents results of the survey first round (from September 2015 to January 2016), the data collection will continue for the broader overview of the topic. The second round will start in February 2016 and will include questionnaires in Lithuanian for the respondents from Lithuania.

IV. CHARACTERISTIC OF THE SURVEY RESPONDENTS

Majority of the respondents is female. The average age of the respondents from Lithuania and Spain is 21 year as the majority of them are bachelor students and according to the set research methodology the age of the respondents from these country were set in frames of 18 to 24 years inclusive. Respondents from Latvia are Master's students – all student of the PA program of the University of Latvia. Their average age is 28 years.

72.70% of Latvian respondents would like to work for public organization. Only 12.50% of them was an entrepreneur and 12.50% of them were unemployed looking for any job. All other respondents already work for public organizations. 75.80% of Lithuanian respondents also preferred to work for public organization and 36.00% of these respondents worked for public organizations. In total 39.39% of the Lithuanian respondents were employed (Table II). The majority of the respondents most probably correctly chose the field of the studies considering employability preferences.

The case of Spain differs. 50.00% of the respondents would like to work for private organizations. Out of 35.70% employed respondents only 30.00% worked in public sector (Table II). This reflect the respondents' uncertainty about the field of studies and of preferred field of work.

The respondents were asked to evaluate a probability of working in a number of different fields of occupation using 10-point scale, where 1-is not probable at all, 10 – extremely probable (Table III). On average, all three countries respondents gave the first priority to PA and security, compulsory social insurance as their probable area of work.

TABLE II
CHARACTERISTICS OF THE RESPONDENTS

Criterion/ Country	Latvia	Lithuania	Spain
Average age, years	28	21	21
Female, %	90.91	76.00	57.00
Male, %	9.09	24.00	43.00
Wished to work for a private organization, %	27.30	27.20	50.00
Wished to work for a public organization, %	72.70	75.80	50.00
Bachelor student (first degree), %	0.00	81.80	100.00
Bachelor student (second degree), %	0.00	3.05	0.00
Master's student (first degree), %	91.00	12.10	0.00
Master student (second degree), %	9.00	3.05	0.00
Employed, %	81.82	39.39	35.70
Employed in private organization, %	0.00	12.12	25.00
Employed in public organization, %	81.82	30.30	10.71
Entrepreneur, %	9.09	0.00	3.03

TABLE III
RESPONDENTS MEAN PROBABILITY OF WORKING IN A NUMBER OF AREAS BY COUNTRY

Area/ Country	Latvia	Lithuania	Spain
Accommodation and catering services	3.636	5.719	5.000
Activities of extraterritorial organizations and bodies	4.727	5.844	6.037
Administrative and support service activities	6.545	7.500	7.037
Agriculture, Forestry and Fisheries	3.182	4.188	2.444
Arts, entertainment and leisure	5.818	5.344	3.296
Construction	2.545	4.188	2.481
Education	5.545	6.500	5.148
Electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning supply	3.364	4.500	2.185
Financial and insurance activities	4.727	5.719	6.222
Household as employer; undifferentiated goods and services producing activities that household creates for its own use	3.364	5.469	3.370
Human health and social work activities	5.545	7.313	3.963
Information and communication	7.000	7.938	5.259
Manufacturing	3.091	5.375	3.148
Mining and quarrying	3.273	4.125	2.000
Professional, scientific and technical services	4.455	5.250	4.519
PA and security, compulsory social insurance	8.455	7.750	8.407
Real estate	5.091	6.188	2.778
Transportation and Storage	3.000	5.031	3.111
Water supply; sewerage, waste management and remediation activities	3.545	4.438	2.667
Wholesale and retail trade	3.909	4.781	5.111

Another top priority of all respondents is Administrative and support service activities. Favorable areas among the respondents of Latvia and Lithuania are also Information and communication, Real estate, and Human health and social work activities. Respondents from Lithuania and Spain with quite high probability on average noted such areas as Financial and insurance activities, and Activities of extraterritorial organizations and bodies.

The least popular areas among the respondents from Latvia and Spain were Construction, Electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning supply, and Transportation and Storage. Mining and quarrying as well as Agriculture, Forestry and Fisheries had one of the smallest probability on average between all respondents. Respondents from Spain noted Water supply; sewerage, waste management and remediation activities with

very low probability as an area of their future work (Table III).

Survey respondents have a number of commonalities and differences depending of the country of origin. They are young students (except the students from Latvia, who are averagely older, because the age that was excluded as criterion conducting the survey in Latvia). Some of them are already employed, many of employed students are working for the public organizations. It is possible to conclude that the majority of the students connected their choice of the study program with their plans on employability areas. However, there are students, who would prefer to work in private sector in spite of studying PA or other relevant study area.

V. THE SURVEY RESULTS ON THE STUDENTS PREFERENCES CONSIDERING ON A FUTURE EMPLOYER

Exploring respondents' preferences considering on a future employer, they were offered to evaluate a number of criteria by their importance using 10-point scale, where 1 - *is not important at all*, 10 - *extremely important*. All criteria were split to three groups i.e. elements of Employer Branding (EB), organizations evaluation areas used by the Sustainability Index (SI) [27] of an organization and Social Responsibility (SR) principles [28].

Fig. 1 Aspects importance for respondents considering on a future employer by country *Organization that the respondent is considering to work for (employer i.e. public or private institution or a company/enterprise)

On average, all observed countries' respondents evaluated importance of good employer brand, social responsibility, and inclusion in different kind of recognized ratings of the considered future employer high from 6.182 to 8.667 points (Fig. 1). All countries respondents' priority, however, is social responsibility of their future employer, while the least important for the respondents from Latvia and Spain is employer's inclusion in different kind of recognized rating, while the respondents from Lithuania on average evaluate equally both aspects employer's inclusion in different kind of recognized rating and good employer brand (Fig. 1).

For the respondents from each observed country are important different principles of Social Responsibility. On average, all respondents evaluated importance of all SR principles high i.e. from 7.720 to 9.545 points (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2 Social Responsibility principles importance for respondents considering on a future employer by country

The most important SR principle for the respondents (Fig. 2) from Latvia is *respect for human rights* (9.545 points on average), from Lithuanian – *respect for the rule of law* (9.129), and from Spain – *transparency* (9.000). These results could also illustrate opinion of respondents on local employers' problems and respondents' values as employees. As the least important SR principles considering on a future employer (Fig. 2), the respondents from Latvia and Spain evaluated *respect for international norms of behavior* (7.727 and 7.750 points on average relatively), and respondents from Lithuania and Spain – *respect for stakeholder interests* (8.194 and 7.786). Most probably the respondents did not recognize that one of these stakeholder can be the organization's future or current employees.

The respondents were also evaluated by importance considering on a future employer used by the Sustainability Index organizations evaluation areas i.e. organization activity in the certain area (Fig. 3). The respondents on average evaluated high all these areas i.e. from 6.636 to 9.323 points. All three countries respondents on average as the most important aspect evaluated *work environment*. The least important for the respondents from Latvia and Spain is a futures employer's activity in area of *environment* (6.636 and 7.429 points on average relatively) e.g. paper recycling or water consumption optimization, for the respondents from Lithuania – *market relations* (7.581) e.g. relations with partners or clients (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3 Used by the Sustainability Index organizations evaluation areas importance for respondents considering on a future employer by country

TABLE IV
EMPLOYER BRANDING ELEMENTS' IMPORTANCE FOR THE RESPONDENTS
CONSIDERING ON A FUTURE EMPLOYER BY COUNTRY

EB element/ Country	Latvia	Lithuania	Spain
What the organization* is	5.636	8.467	7.464
What organization* offers for employees	9.364	8.867	8.286
Organizational* processes (vision, mission, goals)	6.818	8.467	7.893
What kind of employees employed	8.455	8.333	7.071
What is expected from employees	8.000	8.800	8.107
Internal communication	8.545	8.667	8.571
Rewards and recognition	8.273	8.733	8.857
Learning and development	8.000	8.933	8.964
Service support	6.909	8.533	8.607
Measurement system	7.455	8.200	6.571
Current culture and ethics in the organization	8.545	8.667	7.500
Job opportunities	8.727	9.133	8.821
Job learning opportunities	8.727	9.267	8.607
Key functions and specific characteristics	8.364	8.400	7.536
Introduction program for new employees	7.273	8.733	8.143
Advancement opportunities	9.273	8.733	8.607
Career programs	8.636	9.067	8.036
Benefits and compensation system	8.273	8.867	8.393
Working environment	9.000	9.133	8.393
Recruitment and induction	8.000	8.667	6.857
Team management	8.000	8.667	7.536
Performance appraisal	8.455	8.267	7.250
Past achievements	6.364	7.933	6.964
Social activities, sponsorship etc.	6.636	8.467	6.286
Products and services ratings	7.545	8.467	6.714

*Organization that the respondent is considering to work for (employer i.e. public or private institution or a company/enterprise)

The importance of Employer Brand elements of the future employer also was evaluated quite high on average by all respondents i.e. from 5.636 to 9.364 points (Table IV). The most and the least important elements are different for each country's respondents. The most important EB element considering on a future employer for the respondents from Latvia is *what organization offers for employees* (9.364 points on average), from Lithuania – *job learning opportunities* (9.267), and from Spain - *learning and development* (8.964). The respondents from Latvia are interested on the employer general list of offers, while respondents from Lithuania and Spain emphasize a specific offer of the employer connected to professional development and life-long learning possibilities offered by the employer for the employees. The least important elements for the respondents are *what the organization* is including its values, goals, mission etc. (5.636 points on average by the respondents from Latvia), *past achievements* such as financial or social achievements (7.933 points on average by the respondents from Lithuania), and *social activities, sponsorship etc.* (6.286 points on average by the respondents from Spain). To consider on working for the certain employer or not the respondents from Lithuania and Spain would rather ignore the employer past achievements and active participation in social activities i.e. activities of the community, however, they had outlined that organization's social responsibility is quite curtail factor for them choosing

the future employer. This fact makes to conclude that the respondents do not realize that social activity of the organization as well as its activity in the issues of environment is a part of its SR implementation. Respondents from Latvia most probably will not be loyal and engaged employees as they would rather ignore the goals, mission and values of their employers. This might mean that they are not going to work for any employer because of the organizational culture rather because of some benefits that they can get from the employer such as salary, learning opportunities, positive and comfortable working environment etc. This is one of the typical generation Y characteristics.

HRR implementers might use this results as an evidence that generation Y representatives have common characteristics and values as job seekers and employees. This results will help to improve organization itself, developing its employer brand and external positioning, manifestation and popularization of the certain characteristics and work results that as a result will help to attract such young job seekers as the respondents of the study are.

VI. THE SURVEY RESULTS ON THE STUDENTS PECULIARITIES AND HABITS SORTING JOB ADVERTISEMENTS AND SEARCHING FOR A JOB

To help to identify preferences and peculiarities of the respondents as job seekers screening the job advertisements and considering on application to the vacant positions based on the information from the advertisements, few more questions were asked. First of all, they were asked to evaluate importance of information in a job advertisement when considering an application for an offered position using the same 10-point scale. The evaluation was different some kinds of information the respondents evaluated quite low giving 4.455 points on average, some - really high giving 9.364 points on average (Table V).

Preferred information for the respondents from all countries was *offers for employee* (e.g. *motivational salary, active work environment, etc.*) and *working hours and place*. The respondents from Latvia (9.273 points on average) and Spain (9.000) also evaluated high job advertisement's information on *job responsibilities/occupation objectives* considering on application for the offered position.

At least important information for the respondents from Spain is *name of employer* (5.821 points on average). Most probably they might easily apply for the position not the employer based on the biases on the employer brand that also proof that these respondents have a typical characteristic of the generation Y representatives – they are not loyal to employer [6], [11], [13], [14], they would rather find an interesting job. These respondents most probably are open to the job advertisements created by the recruitment companies that sometimes do not include their client's name in the job advertisement just briefly describing the employer. For some people this kind of advertisement could look suspicious, nonetheless not for the respondents of the survey from Spain.

TABLE V
JOB ADVERTISEMENT'S KINDS OF INFORMATION IMPORTANCE FOR THE RESPONDENTS CONSIDERING AN APPLICATION FOR AN OFFERED POSITION BY COUNTRY

Information by type/ Country	Latvia	Lithuania	Spain
Application instructions / competition description	7.727	7.733	7.357
Documents required for application	6.545	8.467	7.643
Introduction text and/or employer description	6.909	8.400	7.607
Job responsibilities/occupation objectives	9.273	8.533	9.000
Logo of employer	4.455	7.200	5.964
Name of a vacant position	8.000	7.667	6.643
Name of employer	7.909	7.267	5.821
Offers for employee (e.g. motivational salary, active work environment, etc.)	8.909	8.800	8.714
Requirements for an applicant	8.818	8.200	8.321
Working hours and place	9.364	9.000	8.714

A job advertisement is not an advertisement of a product; therefore, the offered position would not look more attractive for the survey respondents if it has a *logo of the employer* on it especially taking into account that the respondents from Spain even could ignore the name of the employer considering on application for an offered position. All countries' respondents evaluated *logo of employer* as the least important information in the job advertisement comparing to other pieces of information (Table V).

Considering that the generation Y representatives are tended to searching for benefits [6], [11], [13], [14], the next question asked to the survey participants was "How certain kind of information in the job advertisement's offers part is important when considering an application for an offered position?" also using the same ten point scale.

Respondents from Lithuania on average evaluated all offers high giving more than 8 points on average (Table VI). The least important offer for them is *a room for creativity on the working place* (8.063 points on average). The least important offer for the respondents from Latvia and Spain is *work in a multicultural environment* (5.818 and 6.071 points on average relatively). Most probably it is not necessary factor for the respondents or it is not a unique offer for the organizations in these countries i.e. multicultural environment at working place is a usual practice.

For all countries' respondents, salary is a top importance information from the job advertisement offers section (Table VI). Other offers that were evaluated by 8.857 and more points on average are (Table VI):

- 1) Career/professional growth possibilities (9.091 points on average by the respondents from Latvia and 8.857 points on average by the respondents from Spain).
- 2) Flexible working hours (9.063 points on average by the respondents from Lithuania).
- 3) Insurance (9.250 points on average by the respondents from Lithuania).
- 4) Learning opportunities (9.000 points on average by the respondents from Lithuania).

TABLE VI
JOB ADVERTISEMENT'S OFFERS PART'S KINDS OF INFORMATION IMPORTANCE FOR THE RESPONDENTS CONSIDERING AN APPLICATION FOR AN OFFERED POSITION BY COUNTRY

Information by type/ Country	Latvia	Lithuania	Spain
A room for creativity on the working place	7.364	8.063	6.464
Benefits	8.091	8.250	8.607
Career/Professional growth possibilities	9.091	8.875	8.857
Challenging tasks	6.727	8.188	7.321
Distant work possibilities	5.636	8.563	7.357
Fast Career/Professional growth possibilities	7.364	8.625	7.429
Flexible working hours	7.364	9.063	8.607
Insurance	6.909	9.250	8.750
Learning opportunities	8.000	9.000	8.000
Personal working equipment with possibility to use them outside working hours (e.g. a smartphone, laptop, car, etc.)	6.818	8.500	7.393
Professional development possibilities	7.909	8.813	8.571
Salary	9.182	9.500	9.071
Salary that partly depends on the working results	8.455	8.563	8.464
Social and medical benefits	8.455	8.938	8.286
Work in a multicultural environment	5.818	8.188	6.071

To attract the job seekers like the survey respondents, it is not enough to create an eye-catching job advertisement adapted for them, it is important to choose the appropriate job advertisements distribution channel. The last survey participants question helped to identify the respondents' most popular job searching sources.

91% of the respondents from Latvia uses *job search engines on advertisements' portals*, 55% of the respondents ask their *friends and relatives* on a job position for them or check particular *organizations' webpages vacancies/job offers sections*. Only 27% are looking for the vacant positions on the *National Labour Agency WEB page*.

Like in case of Latvia, the most popular job search sources among the respondents from Lithuania are *job search engines on advertisements' portals* (84% of the respondents use them searching for a job) and *friends and relatives* (56%). Also the least popular tool searching for the job for the respondents from Lithuania is *Lithuanian Labour Exchange WEB page* (only 16% of the respondents usually use it searching for the job).

In case of Spain, majority of the respondents emphasized the same tools/ sources and approaches of job searching as the respondents from Latvia and Lithuania, namely 74% of the respondents use *job search engines on local advertisements' portals* and 52% ask *friends/relatives* for help. However, one of the popular tool among the respondents from Spain was different from those top tools that were mentioned by the respondents from Latvia and Lithuania. 56% of the respondents from Spain visit *particular organizations' WEB pages. National Public Employment Service WEB page* (41% of the respondents uses it) is more popular job searching tool for the respondents from Spain than the local equivalents for the respondents from Latvia and Lithuania. The least popular source of the job searching among the respondents from Spain is *advertisements at university*, only 19% of the respondents use them.

None from all three countries' respondents marked *organizations' open doors days* as one of the usual approach of job searching. All these data show that the respondents as generation Y representatives are savvy, technology users that like to learn new things, gather new knowledge, and develop professional skills at work. The HRR implementers can use the study results to realize the importance of the youngest labor market participants' peculiarities and be ready for the rational action.

VII. CONCLUSION

The survey results reflected that the youth from the sample has the typical for generation Y characteristics. Potential and current employers of these students could pay attention on these peculiarities and use them developing HRR process and all other related to this process HR Management activities.

The students from the sample as the typical generation Y representatives are active WEB resources users. However, searching for a job the majority of them use likewise networking advantages and try to find a job via friends and/or family members.

Generation Y representatives from different countries have some slight differences in habits, but not values. This conclusion is based on the survey results presented. Generally, the survey participants considering applying for a vacant position, are sorting job offers by learning, professional development and growth opportunities provided by the employer. The top criterion for them is salary offered. Developing a job advertisement employer should emphasize both offers for the employee and job responsibilities/occupation objectives to attract generation Y representatives.

Employers also should work on positive working environment development and respect of human rights and law as well as be socially responsible implementing not trivial SR activities (employer's sponsorships are at least important for the survey respondents considering on working for that employer).

In spite of the fact that the End of History illusion [17] takes place, some generation Y as job seekers and employees most probably will be the same after ten or twenty years i.e. the employers should admit the necessity of adaptation to the generation Y peculiarities to ensure retention of HR and their best performance. Exploration of generation Y representatives as job seekers is organization's work mainly with external organizational environment that is important implementing HRR nowadays. The research results are valuable for both public and private sector employers as they show that majority of the generation Y representatives from the sample have typical for their generation characteristics.

The author continues to conduct survey in all mentioned countries to obtain more data for a broader examination of the study population.

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